

INFLUENCE OF ZERO LOCATION ON LOGARITHMIC MODULI OF ANALYTIC FUNCTIONS

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ABSTRACT. We analyze $\log |f(z)|$ of analytic functions $f(z)$ on a disc $\mathbb{D}(0, R)$, assuming that f is positive at R . By applying the Poisson-Jensen formula, we separate the influence of inner and outer zeros of f , regarding $\partial\mathbb{D}(0, R)$. For real symmetric inner zeros, we establish a sufficient criterion for a stationary point of $\log |f(x)|$ on $(0, R)$ to exist. The criterion is $\sum \Re(a_j)/|a_j|^2 > C_H$, where the a_j are the inner zeros, and C_H is the log derivative of the harmonic part of $\log |f|$ at 0. [10.5281/zenodo.17766896](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17766896)

1. INTRODUCTION

In this paper we investigate the impact of certain zeros of a complex function $f(z)$ on stationary points of the logarithmic modulus $g(z) = \log |f(z)|$. f is supposed to be analytic in the disc $\mathbb{D}(0, R)$, and R is chosen to be close to 1 in our applications. From our analysis, the presence of real symmetric pairs of zeros a_j in $\mathbb{D}(0, R)$ (so called inner zeros) implies, under rather weak conditions, the existence of at least one stationary point x_* of $\log |f(z)|$ in the segment $(0, R)$. The main device of the method presented is the fact, that through Poisson-Jensen, despite a complicated or difficult behavior of zeros on the border or outside of $\mathbb{D}(0, R)$, the behavior in the inner of $\mathbb{D}(0, R)$ is highly controllable. When applied to the zeta transform, we can therefore exclude all influence of standard non-trivial zeros (i.e. zeros on the critical line), including the essential singularity at 1.

We now provide an outline of the argumentation. Using the Poisson-Jensen formula we obtain the decomposition

$$g(x) = \log |f(z)| = h(z) + \sum_j \log |z - a_j|, \quad z \in \mathbb{D}(0, R),$$

where h is harmonic and the sum runs over the interior zeros of f . By the maximum principle, all (potential) boundary or outer zeros of f are harmonically neutral (i.e. subsumed in h) and cannot influence the curvature of g on $(0, R)$. More precisely, $h(x)$ is smooth on $(0, R)$ and has no stationary points there. We demonstrate further, that (potential) inner zeros a_j can disrupt that behavior and cause the existence of a stationary point of $g(x)$ on $(0, R)$, under certain conditions (see Figure 1). We assume for simplicity that the inner zeros occur in real-symmetric pairs, resulting in double log-singularities real-symmetric to the $(0, R)$ segment, which influence the curvature of g' . Figuratively speaking, the zero singularities pull the graph of the harmonic part $h(x)$ downwards.

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FIGURE 1. In this example, we transform the sine function so that all its roots lie precisely on the unit circle. In the first row, you see the 3D plot of the harmonic part, i.e. the mapped sine without additional zeros in the unit disc, and the according graph over the segment $(0, R)$. In the second row, you see the zero $a_1 = 0.3 + 0.1i$ and its conjugate added to the function, and the acc. impact on the curvature of the harmonic graph over $(0, R)$.

We derive a simple existence criterion for a stationary point by considering the limits of the derivative $g'(x)$ as x approaches the boundaries of the interval $(0, R)$. Since g' is continuous on $(0, R)$, if the one-sided limits satisfy $\lim_{x \rightarrow 0^+} g'(x) < 0$ and $\lim_{x \rightarrow R^-} g'(x) > 0$, the Intermediate Value Theorem guarantees the existence of at least one stationary point (where $g'(x) = 0$) within the interval.

We compute $g'(0^+)$ explicitly and prove that, under the assumption $\lim_{x \rightarrow R} \frac{d}{dx} \log |H(x)| = M > 0$, the existence of a stationary point in $(0, R)$ follows from the condition

$$\sum_j \frac{\Re a_j}{|a_j|^2} > \frac{C_H}{2}, \quad \text{where } C_H = \left. \frac{d}{dx} \log |H(x)| \right|_{x=0}.$$

2. STATIONARY POINTS OF $\log |f|$ ON $(0, R)$

We comprise the prerequisites for the existence of a stationary point of the logarithmic modulus $g(x) = \log |f(x)|$ in the unit disc \mathbb{D} in the following theorem.

Let $\mathbb{D}(0, R)$ be a disc with radius $R < 1$, centered at 0. Let further f be analytic in $\mathbb{D}(0, R)$, continuous on $\overline{\mathbb{D}(0, R)}$, and admit the factorisation

$$f(z) = H(z) \prod_{j=1}^N (z - a_j)(z - \bar{a}_j), \quad a_j \in \mathbb{D}(0, R),$$

where H is analytic and non-vanishing in $\mathbb{D}(0, R)$. I.e. the inner zeros occur in real-symmetric pairs (which is important in the following calculations). Define

$$g(x) = \log |f(x)|, \quad x \in (0, R), \quad C_H := \left. \frac{d}{dx} \log |H(x)| \right|_{x=0}.$$

Assume the growth condition

$$(G) \quad \lim_{x \rightarrow R} \frac{d}{dx} \log |H(x)| = M > 0.$$

Theorem 2.1 (stationary point criterion for log modulus). *Under the above assumptions, if*

$$\sum_{j=1}^N \frac{\Re a_j}{|a_j|^2} > \frac{C_H}{2},$$

then $g'(0^+) < 0$. Together with (G), this implies the existence of $x_* \in (0, R)$ with $g'(x_*) = 0$. Hence g has at least one stationary point in $(0, R)$.

Proof of Theorem 2.1. We first record a standard decomposition of $\log |f|$ inside the disc. Let $\mathbb{D}(0, R)$ be a disc with radius R , centered at 0.

Lemma 2.2 (Poisson–Jensen decomposition). *Let f be analytic and not identically zero in $\mathbb{D}(0, R)$, continuous on $\overline{\mathbb{D}}(0, R)$, and let $\{a_k\}$ denote its zeros in $\mathbb{D}(0, R)$, counted with multiplicities. Then for every $z \in \mathbb{D}(0, R)$ one has*

$$\log |f(z)| = h(z) + \sum_k \log |z - a_k|,$$

where h is harmonic in $\mathbb{D}(0, R)$. Zeros of f on $\partial\mathbb{D}(0, R)$ or outside of $\mathbb{D}(0, R)$ are absorbed entirely into the harmonic term h .

Proof. The Poisson–Jensen formula in the unit disc (see Conway [2, Sec. 11]) states that for $z = re^{i\theta} \in \mathbb{D}(0, R)$,

$$\log |f(z)| = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} P_r(\theta - \varphi) \log |f(e^{i\varphi})| d\varphi - \sum_k \log \left| \frac{1 - \overline{a_k}z}{z - a_k} \right|.$$

The Poisson integral is harmonic in z , hence contributes a harmonic function $h_1(z)$. Each zero term satisfies

$$-\log \left| \frac{1 - \overline{a_k}z}{z - a_k} \right| = \log |z - a_k| + h_{2,k}(z),$$

where $h_{2,k}$ is harmonic in $\mathbb{D}(0, R)$ because $\log |1 - \overline{a_k}z|$ is harmonic there. Summing over k we obtain

$$\log |f(z)| = h_1(z) + \sum_k \log |z - a_k| + \sum_k h_{2,k}(z),$$

which is of the asserted form with $h(z) = h_1(z) + \sum_k h_{2,k}(z)$ harmonic in $\mathbb{D}(0, R)$. Boundary or outer zeros do not appear in the Jensen sum and are encoded in the boundary values of $\log |f|$, hence contribute only to h . \square

Proof of Theorem 1.1. We may assume that

$$f(z) = H(z) \prod_{j=1}^N (z - a_j)(z - \overline{a_j}), \quad a_j \in \mathbb{D}(0, R),$$

where H is analytic and non-vanishing in $\mathbb{D}(0, R)$. Any zeros of f on $\partial\mathbb{D}(0, R)$ can be incorporated into H , by Lemma 2.2.

By Lemma 2.2 we have on $\mathbb{D}(0, R)$

$$g(x) = \log |f(z)| = \log |H(z)| + \sum_{j=1}^N \{\log |z - a_j| + \log |z - \bar{a}_j|\}.$$

Restricting to $z = x \in (0, R)$, the term $\log |H(x)|$ is harmonic in a neighbourhood of $(0, R)$, while the logarithmic terms encode precisely the inner zeros a_j . The maximum principle for harmonic functions (see e.g. Conway [1, Thm. X.1.4]) shows that the harmonic term alone cannot create or remove stationary points of g in $(0, R)$. Hence zeros on $\partial\mathbb{D}(0, R)$ or outside of $\mathbb{D}(0, R)$, which have been absorbed in H , are neutral with respect to the existence of such stationary points.

Since H is analytic and non-vanishing in $\mathbb{D}(0, R)$, the function $\log |H(x)|$ is real-analytic on $(-1, 1)$ and its derivative at 0 is C_H by definition.

For each j we write $a_j = \alpha_j + i\beta_j$ with $\beta_j \neq 0$ or $a_j \in (0, 1)$ real; we get

$$|x - a_j|^2 = (x - \alpha_j)^2 + \beta_j^2.$$

(similar for \bar{a}_j). A short calculation yields

$$g'(x) = \frac{d}{dx} \log |H(x)| + \sum_{j=1}^N \frac{2(x - \alpha_j)}{|x - a_j|^2}, \quad x \in (0, 1).$$

Evaluating at $x = 0$ gives

$$g'(0^+) = C_H - 2 \sum_{j=1}^N \frac{\alpha_j}{|a_j|^2} = C_H - 2 \sum_{j=1}^N \frac{\Re a_j}{|a_j|^2}.$$

Apparently, $g'(0^+) < 0$ for

$$\sum_{j=1}^N \frac{\Re a_j}{|a_j|^2} > \frac{C_H}{2},$$

which is our criterion.

Write

$$g'(x) = h'(x) + R(x), \quad h(x) := \log |H(x)|, \quad R(x) := \sum_{j=1}^N \frac{2(x - \Re a_j)}{|x - a_j|^2}.$$

Since each $a_j \in \mathbb{D}(0, R)$ and $a_j \notin (0, R)$, the continuous function $x \mapsto |x - a_j|$ attains a positive minimum on $[0, R]$, which is $\Re a_j$.

Consequently,

$$\left| \frac{2(x - \Re a_j)}{|x - a_j|^2} \right| \leq \frac{2}{\Re a_j^2}, \quad x \in [0, R],$$

and summing over j yields the global bound

$$|R(x)| \leq M := \sum_{j=1}^N \frac{2}{\Re a_j^2} < \infty, \quad x \in [0, R].$$

Now impose the growth condition

$$(G) \quad \lim_{x \rightarrow R} h'(x) = M > 0.$$

Then for $K := M + 1$ there exists $x_1 \in (0, R)$ such that $h'(x_1) > K$. At this point we have

$$g'(x_1) = h'(x_1) + R(x_1) \geq h'(x_1) - |R(x_1)| > (M + 1) - M = 1 > 0.$$

We have thus found a point near 0 with $g'(0^+) < 0$ and a point $x_1 \in (0, 1)$ with $g'(x_1) > 0$. Since g' is continuous on $(0, R)$, the intermediate value theorem yields $x_* \in (0, 1)$ with $g'(x_*) = 0$. Therefore g has a stationary point in $(0, R)$, completing the proof of Theorem 2.1 □

3. EXAMPLE: THE SINUS MODEL

We first present an example of the method. To demonstrate the effect of a scenario where the outer zeros accumulate at 1, similar to the situation given with the zeta transform, we transform the sine function such that all its zeros lie precisely on the unit circle. This results in harmonic behavior within the unit disc, as there are no zeros strictly inside it. We then artificially introduce additional zeros and perform concrete calculations to analyze the results.

Let $R = 1 - \epsilon$, for a small $\epsilon > 0$.

$$f(z) = \left(\prod_{j=1}^N (z - a_j)(z - \bar{a}_j) \right) \sin\left(i \frac{1+z}{1-z}\right), \quad a_j \in \mathbb{D}.$$

The sine factor has all its zeros on $|z| = 1$. For $x \in (0, R)$,

$$\log |H(x)| = \log \sinh\left(\frac{1+x}{1-x}\right), \quad C_H = 2 \coth(1).$$

Since $\frac{d}{dx} \log |H(x)| \sim (1-x)^{-2}$ as $x \rightarrow 1^-$, (G) is satisfied.

The criterion of Theorem 2.1 becomes

$$\sum_{j=1}^N \frac{\Re a_j}{|a_j|^2} > \coth(1) \approx 1.313.$$

If we now consider a specific pair of zeros, for example, $a_1 = 0.3 \pm 0.1i$, the expression evaluates to

$$\frac{\Re a_j}{|a_j|^2} = 3 > 1.313,$$

which results in a stationary point, at $x \approx 0.278714$ (determined numerically).

Figure 1 illustrates the impact of the pair of zeros on the curvature of $\log |H(x)|$ over the segment $(0, R)$.

Note that not every choice of zeros will satisfy the criteria. For instance, with $a_1 = 0.75 + 0.25i$, the expression evaluates to

$$\frac{\Re a_j}{|a_j|^2} = 1.2 < 1.313$$

Furthermore, this specific example does not actually yield a minimum, as can be determined numerically. (It is, of course, possible for certain zero pairs to not satisfy the sufficient criteria yet still yield a minimum.)

In the Figure 2 we visualize the function $s(z) = \frac{\Re z}{|z|^2}$. Level curves on the graph of s define the region of zeros which imply a stationary point.

FIGURE 2. Visualization of the function $s(z) = \frac{\Re z}{|z|^2}$. The blue curve indicates the level set for $s(z) = 1.33$, which represents the threshold value for zero sums that imply a stationary point in the sine model. The red curve shows the projection of the unit circle onto the surface of s .

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